

SHAPE MEMORY BEHAVIOURS OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYURETHANE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

As promising materials for biomedical implantation applications with the ability of recovering shape upon external stimulus and good biocompatibility, shape memory polymers (SMP) suffer from the problems of low stiffness and strength. In this study, carbon fibres (CF) reinforced thermal-induced SMP – two kinds of thermoplastic polyurethane (PU) were fabricated using a hot-pressing of PU films and CF plain woven fabrics. The influence of reinforcement on both mechanical properties and shape memory behaviours were characterised. DMA was used to define T_g of CF/PU composites, and microstructures of CF/PU were assessed using scanning electron microscopy. Fully folded bend recovery tests above and below T_g and three-point bending tests were performed to characterise shape memory behaviours and recovery force of bulk PU and CF/PU composites laminates. The results indicate carbon fibre enhanced the shape memory recovery behaviours above T_g but reduced it below T_g in shape memory. The CF/PU composites also demonstrate much higher recovery forces than the base PU.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs) have been of great interests with the ability to response to a specific external actuation and recover a predetermined shape [1, 2]. Compared to other materials with the properties of shape memory, such as Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs), SMPs have the advantage of lightweight, the ability of high strain and shape recovery, easy processing and adaptation to a variety of applications [3].

Polyurethane (PU) is one of the most versatile polymers used in various forms from coating to fibres in many applications including biomedical applications [4]. Shape Memory Polyurethane (SMPU), has been extensively researched since its discovery by Mitsubishi in 1988, attracting a great deal of attention recently, due to their unique properties such as the wide range of shape recovery temperatures (from -30 °C to 70 °C), high shape recoverability, good process ability and excellent biocompatibility [5]. Shape memory behaviour of biomedical devices enables to efficiently minimise damage caused by surgery. Due to remarkable biocompatibility, SMPU can be used for the deployment of different clinical devices when contacted or implanted in the human body [3], such as vascular stents, catheter, heart valve, and clot extraction devices [6-9].

In spite of good biocompatibility, the unreinforced SMPU suffer from problems of low stiffness and strength [10]. To deal with the limitation of use of SMPU, shape memory polymer composites with particles or fibres have been studied, for example carbon black, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers, Ni, Fe₃O₄, SiC, clay, short fibers and continuous fibres [11], demonstrated with the increased strength and stiffness[12].

In this study, the continuous carbon fibres were used to reinforce SMPU, and shape memory behaviours with aims for biomedical applications were investigated. Recovery behaviours for bending

recovery were investigated above and below the glass transition temperature, and the recovery force was measured using a three-point bend fixture. The surface modification for biocompatibility of the polymers and in vivo tests will be reported elsewhere.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The polyurethane (PU) based thermoplastic shape memory polymers MM2520 and MM4520 (DiAPLEX Co., Ltd, Japan) were used as matrix, with the nominal glass transition temperature (T_g) being 25 °C and 45 °C, respectively. Plain woven carbon fibre (CF) sheets TORAYCA T300J 3K (Toray Carbon Fibers America, Inc.) were used to reinforce the thermal-induced shape memory polymers. The granules of PU polymers were first pressed into films of a thickness of 0.3~0.4 mm using a hot press at a temperature for 200 °C. CF/PU composites were fabricated using a film-stacking technique where two layers of plain woven carbon fibre fabric sheets and three layers of polyurethane films were laid up before hot-pressing at a temperature of 200 °C with a pressure of 0.72 MPa for 10 minutes (MM2520) and 180 °C with a pressure of 1.6 MPa for 30 minutes (MM4520). The carbon fibre volume fraction in the consolidated CF/PU composites was about 23% for CF/PU2520 and 35 % for CF/PU4520. Microstructures of CF/PU composites were examined using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Samples for SEM were sputter-coated with gold and 5kV was applied during observation.

2.2 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) experiments were conducted under the single cantilever mode using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzers 2980 (TA Instruments). The rectangle samples of PU and CF/PU with a size of 40×10×1 mm³ were prepared. The experiments was conducted at a frequency of 1 Hz, an amplitude of 20 μm and a heating rate of 2 °C/min, with a temperature range of -20 °C ~ 200 °C for MM2520, and 0 °C ~ 200 °C for MM4520. T_g was measured as the peak of tangent δ .

2.3 Mechanical properties

Tensile tests were performed on a universal testing machine (Instron 3366) at room temperature around 25 °C, at a cross-head speed of 10 mm/min, according to ASTM D882 and ASTM D3039. Rectangle specimens were used with a gauge length of 25 mm. For CF/PU composites, aluminium tabs were added at the end of specimens. Three point bending tests with a span of 32 mm were conducted on a universal testing machine (Instron 5567) at room temperature around 25 °C as well. Rectangle shape specimens with thickness 1 mm, width 10 mm, and length 50 mm were used. 10 mm pin was chosen and speed of 1 mm/min was applied, consistent with ASTM D7264. At least five specimens were tested for two types of PU and the CF/PU composites.

2.4 Shape memory behaviours

Shape memory behaviours were characterised using fully folded bending recovery tests of bulk PU and CF/PU composites laminates with length 80 mm, width 5 mm, thickness 1 mm. Testing was conducted following the steps:

(1) The specimen was placed in a hot water bath at 65 °C for 5 minutes waiting until reaching a soft rubbery status.

(2) The specimen is bent fully to the maximum angle, $\theta_m = 180^\circ$ around a mandrel ($D = 6$ mm) in the hot water and then transferred to a cool water bath (at 0 °C) and kept there for 5minutes until the shape is fixed at an angle of θ_f .

(3) Taken out from the cool water to another bath at a temperature (T_h), above or below T_g . T_h was set to be $T_g - 20$ °C, $T_g - 10$ °C, T_g °C, $T_g + 10$ °C, $T_g + 20$ °C and 37 °C, where the bending recovery time t , recovered angle θ_r , were measured. The recovery performance and fixed angles θ_f (N)

and the recovery angle $\theta_r(N)$ under cycle tests for 10 times were obtained as well. To describe the recovery behaviours, the fixity rate R_f and recovery rate R_r , were calculated using

$$R_f = \frac{\theta_f(N)}{\theta_m} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$R_r = \frac{\theta_f(N) - \theta_r(N)}{\theta_f(N)} \times 100. \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a bending recovery test.

2.5 Shape recovery force

The recovery force was tested under three point bending mode using a rheometer (Physica MCR 301, Anton Paar), as schematically shown in Figure 2:

- (1) Heat the specimen from room temperature to $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$,
- (2) Maintain the specimen at $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 minutes until a soft rubbery status,
- (3) At temperature $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$, apply a displacement of 2.5 mm at the middle span of specimen,
- (4) Cool down to $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$,
- (5) Maintain the specimen at $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 minutes at the displacement, and
- (6) Heat the specimen from $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ to $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ at $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under loaded to measure the recovery load, F_r , when keeping the displacement.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of a recovery force experiment.

End support and a pin ($D = 3 \text{ mm}$) were added to rheometer, which was able to test recovery force (nominal force in rheology) and control the temperature below and above T_g , precisely. Specimens with a size of $70 \times 10 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ were placed on the support with a span, $l = 56 \text{ mm}$.

Bending recovery force F_r , during heating from $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ to $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$, was obtained by

$$F_r = F_i - F_0, \quad (3)$$

where F_0 [N] was obtained before heating at $T_g - 20$ °C, F_i [N] was measured during heating recovery, $F_i = F_0$ when the heating starts.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology

Figure 3 shows the typical optical micrographs and SEM graphs of side view of CF/PU composites. It can be seen that the PU matrix penetrated into the woven carbon fibres well with excellent impregnation without visible voids though PU4520 and PU2520 have a high viscosity. However, apparently there are PU matrix-rich layers on top and bottom surfaces of the CF/PU composites, which may give different results of modulus of elasticity between uniaxial tension and transverse flexural tests.

Figure 3: SEM of PUs and CF/PU composites. (a) PU2520, (b) PU4520, (c) CF/PU2520, and (d) CF/PU4520, and optical micrographs of (e) CF/PU2520 and (f) CF/PU4520.

3.2 DMA

The relationship of storage modulus E' , tangent δ as a function of temperature is shown in Figure 4, and the key data are summarized in Table 1. With nominal T_g being 25 °C, PU2520 has a T_g of 18.5 °C while CF/PU2520 has 11.1 °C; PU4520 has 41.6 °C and CF/PU4520 has 40.8 °C indeed, with nominal T_g being 45 °C. For both types of PU, T_g of CF/PU composites became lower than pure PUs; this means carbon fibres impose restrictions against molecular motion of polymer chains due to the absorption of matrix on the surface of the fibres. The storage modulus of CF/PU composites was

significantly higher than PUs either below or above T_g , which means larger deformation resistance of CF/PU composites.

Figure 4: Storage modulus E' and tangent δ as a function of temperature. (a) PU2520 and CF/PU2520, (b) PU4520 and CF/PU4520.

3.3 Tensile test

The typical tensile stress-strain curves of PUs and CF/PU composites were shown in Figure 5. In terms of Young's modulus, PU2520 has an average of 23 MPa, while PU4520 has 729 MPa; CF/PU2520 has 19.4 GPa and CF/PU4520 has 35.0 GPa, as outlined in

Table 1. This indicates PU4520 is much stiffer than PU2520, and carbon fibres reinforce PU substantially as expected. The tensile strength of CF/PU4520 is about 301 MPa, which is clearly higher than that of CF/PU2520, attributed to the low volume fraction of carbon fibres in CF/PU2520.

Figure 5: Tensile stress-strain curves of (a) PU2520 and PU4520, (b) CF/PU2520 and CF/PU4520.

3.4 Flexural test

The flexural load-displacement curves were obtained from three point bending tests, as shown in Figure 6. Following the procedure in ASTM D7264, the flexural modulus was calculated. The average flexural modulus of PU2520 is 25 MPa, while PU4520 is 427 MPa, which are consistent with the Young's modulus measured using the tensile tests. With carbon fibre reinforcement, the average flexural modulus of CF/PU2520 is 2.3 GPa while CF/PU4520 is 7.9 GPa, as outlined in

Table 1. For the CF/PU composites, there is a clear difference between the values of flexural

modulus and Young's modulus, which is attributed to a layered structure of CF/PU composites; carbon fibres in the middle layer contribute less to the flexural modulus. The flexural strength at the peak load is 91.2 MPa for CF/PU4520 but 30.3 MPa for CF/PU2520. The difference is consistent to that in the tensile strength.

Figure 6: Typical flexural load-displacement curves of (a) PU2520 and PU4520, (b) CF/PU2520 and CF/PU4520.

Table 1: Properties of PUs and CF/PUs

	Glass transition temperature T_g [°C]	Young's modulus E [GPa]	Tensile strength σ_t [MPa]	Flexural modulus E_{bend} [GPa]	Flexural Strength σ_f [MPa]
PU2520	18.5	0.023±0.001	2.7±0.1*	0.025±0.003	0.5±0.02 [^]
PU4520	41.6	0.73±0.05	23.7±1.9	0.43±0.05	6.9±0.5 [^]
CF/PU2520	11.1	19.4±3.2	117.6±34.7	2.3±0.1	30.3±0.9
CF/PU4520	40.8	35.0±17.9	301.1±20.4	7.9±0.6	91.2±5.6

* At the axial strain of 25 %. [^] at the cross head displacement of 3 mm.

3.5 Shape memory behaviours

Shape memory behaviours were characterised by bending recovery angle θ_r as a function of recovery time, t , under different temperature, T_h . The recovery tests under $T_h = 15^\circ\text{C}$, 25°C , 35°C , 45°C ($T_g - 10^\circ\text{C} \sim T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$) were conducted for PU2520 and CF/PU2520 (Figure 7a), and $T_h = 25^\circ\text{C}$, 35°C , 45°C , 55°C , 65°C ($T_g - 20^\circ\text{C} \sim T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$) for PU4520 and CF/PU4520 (Figure 7b). Above T_g , CF/PU composites recovered faster and more than the bulk PUs at the same temperature, while the CF/PU composites recovered slower and less than bulk PU at the same temperature below T_g . This can be accounted by the presence of carbon fibres that change the mechanical properties of composites significantly. When at a temperature higher than T_g , the high elasticity of carbon fibres reinforce the recovery; however, they resist the recovery of shape memory polymers conversely at a temperature lower than T_g .

At 37°C , being consistent with the human body temperature, higher than T_g of PU2520 and CF/PU2520, but lower than T_g of PU4520 and CF/PU4520, CF/PU2520 performs the fastest recovery because of carbon fibre reinforcement above T_g , and CF/PU4520 showed the slowest recovery attributed to carbon fibre resistance below T_g (Figure 7c).

Figure 7: Bending shape recovery angle as a function of time during heating process. (a) at $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C} \sim T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ for PU2520 and CF/PU2520, (b) PU4520 and CF/PU4520, and (c) PUs and CF/PU composites at 37°C .

The cycle tests of shape memory behaviours above T_g were characterised by fixed angles $\theta_f(N)$ and recovery angle $\theta_r(N)$ as a function of number of cycles N at different temperature T_h . For each cycle, the fixity rate R_f and recovery rate R_r , were calculated to describe the shape recoverability. The shape recoverability of PU4520, CF/PU2520 and CF/PU4520 were shown in Figure 8, as PU2520 occurred failure after a few cycles. Compared with 2520 series, 4520 series had higher fixity rate, and it declined more smoothly with the number of cycles. Meanwhile, carbon fibres played a negative role in the fixation of CF/PU composites (Figure 8a). When it comes to recovery rate (Figure 8b), carbon fibres exerted a positive effect on recovery of CF/PU composites as CF/PU4520 had a higher value of recovery rate than PU4520, both at $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ and especially $T_g + 10^\circ\text{C}$. This is due to at $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$, pure PUs are able to recover to the maximum extent equal to CF/PU composites, but at $T_g + 10^\circ\text{C}$, PUs without carbon fibres do not possess the potential to recover as much as CF/PU composites do. The reason why the recovery rates of CF/PU2520 here overtook that of CF/PU4520 can be attributed to the fact that the actual T_g of CF/PU2520 was 11°C (about 14°C lower than nominal T_g), which meant a temperature of 35°C ($T_g + 10^\circ\text{C}$ set for CF/PU2520) was equivalent to $T_g + 24^\circ\text{C}$. However, CF/PU2520 performs unstable and worse fixity and recovery in the cycle testing, which was associated with buckled fracture of materials. Pure PU2520 without carbon fibres happened fracture during early stage of cycling test, and similarly CF/PU2520 had buckled fracture even carbon fibres connected the bulk materials until the end of test. Overall, 2520 series are not capable to sustain the integrity of materials after recovery of several times, but a stable shape recoverability of CF/PU4520 can be expected after several numbers of recovery cycles.

Figure 8: Bending recovery ratios of PUs and CF/PU as a function of number of cycles. (a) fixity rate and (b) recovery rate.

3.6 Shape recovery force

Figure 9a showed the shape recovery of pure PUs incurred during $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ to T_g only, and the recovery force first increased reaching a peak of about 0.5 mN at T_g but started to diminish when the temperature was above T_g . In the view of the possibility that there is a delay between the actual temperature in specimen and the temperature set up for the testing chamber, the peak of recovery force happened above T_g recorded for the chamber. The negative recovery force of bulk PUs after $T_g + 10^\circ\text{C}$ may be due to thermal expansion of PUs above T_g . As for the CF/PU composites, the shape recovery force kept increasing during the heating process from $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ to $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ (Figure 9b). Elasticity of carbon fibres may have accounted for the behaviour, overriding the behaviour of PUs.

The recovery force of pure PUs was much lower than CF/PU composites. The maximum values of recovery force of PU2520, PU4520, CF/PU2520 and CFPU4520 were 0.95 mN, 0.85 mN, 0.18 N, and 0.26 N, respectively. This means carbon fibres reinforce the recovery force definitely. There was not a big difference between recovery forces of two bulky PUs; the difference in volume fraction of carbon fibres can be considered as the reason why CF/PU4520 recovered more strongly than CF/PU2520 did, as the former has a clearly higher flexural modulus.

Figure 9: Shape recovery force during heating from $T_g - 20^\circ\text{C}$ to $T_g + 20^\circ\text{C}$ of (a) PU2520 and PU4520, (b) CF/PU2520 and CF/PU4520.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the basic characterisation and shape memory behaviours of carbon fibre reinforced shape memory polyurethane composites were investigated experimentally. Carbon fibres improved the

mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus, flexural modulus and recovery force. Their influence on shape memory recovery was composed of enhancement above T_g and resistance below T_g . If several numbers of cycling recovery is applied, stable shape recoverability of certain CF/PU composites can be expected.

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